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[Deliverable 5.2 – Educational scenarios and tasks for CAV relevant training situations

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List of contributors

Section	Author(s)	Reviewer
1	Luc Vandenabeele Alexandre Baudet	Maxime Larique Patrick van Egmond
2	Ian Fido Luca Pellicciari Lucia Vecere Valerio Vella	Maxime Larique Patrick van Egmond
3	Luc Vandenabeele	Maxime Larique

	Ian Fido Alexandre Baudet	Patrick van Egmond
4, 5, 6	ALL	Maxime Larique Patrick van Egmond

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List of acronyms	
Acronym	Meaning
ACI	Automobile Club d'Italia (IT)
LIST	Luxembourg Institute of Technology (LU)

RDS	Rds Driving Services Limited (UK)
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
WP	Work Package
CAV	Connected and Autonomous Vehicles
L2/L3/L4/L5	Level 2/3/4/5 (for driving automation)
HSS	Home Study Simulator

Notice

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Executive summary

PAsCAL is a user-centric research project funded under the “Horizon 2020” Research and Innovation program aimed at accelerating the user-friendly evolution of connected, cooperative, and automated vehicles and transport systems, by addressing important issues relating to the role of humans in this evolution, in particular appropriate interactions of the autonomous vehicle with different road users including non-drivers.

The literature review and outcomes of the HSS experiment carried out in D4.2 highlighted that trainings are among the factors influencing the driver’s understanding of CAVs and impacting their behaviour and acceptance.

Based on the drivers’ competence and cognitive models (see D5.1) as well as the features requirements for a simulated CAV environment proposing several ways and variables to investigate determinants of a safe takeover, this deliverable describes the training modules proposed during the simulator-based training sessions experimented in the two driving schools’ partners in Italy and in UK.

These modules are articulated between a CAV dedicated theoretical approach and a more practical one using the features developed in the Home Study Simulator.

The theoretical modules are in line with the local laws and common driver training policies of each partner country. These include the taxonomy of autonomous driving levels, the legal perspectives, some explanations of additional dedicated features available in CAV.

The practical modules include preparatory elements for the effective use of the simulator and address several scenarios, proposing various situations occurring in an urban and a Motorway environment, where the take back control process is important. For each of them a description of the expected driver response behaviour is given as well as good practices for the driving instructor to be transmitted during the simulation training sessions.

Outcomes and findings from the simulator-based training sessions carried out in Italy and in UK are reported in the deliverable D5.3.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and organization of the document

WP5 aims at investigating new "driver" training needs and certification requirements for new technologies/levels of automation, understanding how CAV users and non-users cognitively perceive and treat situations in CAV, developing and pre-testing training solutions to enhance driver's behaviour in different scenarios.

Following simulator requirements definition and hypothetical driver models (competency, cognitive and affective models) in D5.1, this deliverable (D5.2) presents educational scenarios and tasks for CAV relevant training situations.

The main section of this document is focusing on the description of the training modules and is articulated as follows: It starts with some preliminary notes and elements of the training approach. Then it presents the theoretical modules taking into account the context of countries of both PAsCAL's driving-school partners (i.e., Italia and UK) and finishes with the practical modules using the Home Study Simulator (HSS). The HSS is a client application installed on a PC, a steering wheel, and a cloud architecture to store the data collected. The HSS allow drivers to test a simulated L3 or L4 CAV with different events (roundabouts, crossroads, etc.) in an urban or a motorway environment.

1.2 Intended audience of this document

The audience for this document is (1) the consortium members of the PAsCAL project, (2) researchers, driving schools and driver trainers/instructors and their Associations (e.g., European Driving Schools Association, Approved Driving Instructors National Joint Council (UK)) and all stakeholders with interest in CAV skills and development, and (3) the European Commission.

2 Description of the training modules

In order to meet emerging driver training needs and certification requirements for new technologies/level of automation and to understand how CAV users and non-users cognitively treat situations in CAV, PAsCAL WP5 partners have developed and pre-tested training solutions to enhance driver's behaviour and acceptance in different scenarios that are presented in this section.

As a preamble, the training approach is described. Then theoretical and practical modules with the Home Study Simulator (HSS) are developed.

It should be noted that existing driver training syllabuses are module based to aid the flow of training and make the acquisition of new skills more easily achievable by all. Hence the approach taken within this section to discuss new training modules.

Each of the modules described in this section are summarised by a table showing their title, a short description, its audience, as well as the link with the related CAV skills defined in deliverable D5.1. which sets out requirements and competence models for CAV relevant training situations. They also mention, for information, examples of content that can be used as a basis for trainers to create their own course material.

2.1 Training approach and preliminary notes

This section first discusses the consequences that technological development has on the responsibilities of drivers and on the right behaviours to adopt for safe driving. These elements have an impact on how to inform and train drivers on the correct behaviour, even in the case of partially or fully autonomous vehicles.

Since the experts of the Italian (Ready2GO) and English (RED) driving schools participate in the experimentation of the proposed methodology for the training of L3 and 4 CAVs, a brief examination of the rules governing the responsibilities of driving vehicles in the two countries, in order to understand what limits and what evolution can be envisaged in this regard.

ACI Ready2Go is a national network of driving schools, to which legally recognized Italian driving schools can join. The Network aims to increase the

educational quality for students through innovative teaching tools, such as the virtual driving simulator, and an Integrative Method both theoretical and practical, in addition to the traditional teaching required by law in order to create more motorists. aware and safe. The Network currently consists of over 200 driving schools located throughout Italy.

RED Driver Training (RDS) operates one of the largest driving schools in the UK with some 1500 Approved Driving Instructors (ADI's) operating under franchise. In addition, RED is responsible for training nearly 15% of all new driving instructors in the UK every year and is an active member of the Approved Driving Instructor National Joint Council (ADINJC) of the UK.

2.1.1 Legal aspects

In both Civil Law and Common Law, vehicle driving is considered a risky activity, which requires complex skills and competences to be acquired through official training, exams, and tests.

Before commencing to write new, or amending existing training modules, careful consideration must be given to the prevailing legal, insurance and liability elements of each country of the participant partners, namely Italy for Ready2go and UK for RED, in addition to the international convention.

Briefly we will next set out the international convention rules and what each of the partners had to consider within their own legal systems before writing the training modules.

Assisted and automated driving calls for different theoretical and practical skills that drivers need to have. In 2017, the amendment to article 8 of the Convention on Road Traffic was approved (UNECE, 2017). The Convention (1993) is an international treaty establishing standard traffic rules, which the seventy-two contracting States have progressively adopted by modifying their national legislation.

Previously, article 8 stated: "Every driver shall at all times be able to control his vehicle". The new wording says: "Every driver shall always be present and able to take control of the vehicle, whose system must allow to be overridden or switched off at any time". Differently from the original text, the Treaty now

implies that drivers of fully or partially automated vehicles are allowed to take their hands off the steering wheel, provided they can switch off the automated system in any moment.

It follows that the relevant international regulation has not been yet amended to the extent of authorizing high-level automated and autonomous driving. The reason is that, in general, the current road and connected infrastructure does not guarantee that this technology – which is nearly to be produced – work safely. In preparation for this advancement, it is up to the various States to regulate the relative pilot research and start revising the legislation (article 8).

Unlike in the past, the driving style will no longer be determined by the driver's behaviour only, but also by the automated systems, which are regulated and maintained according to protocols, instructions, and indications provided by other subjects, professionals and specialists of the various sectors involved. As a result, the human driver's responsibility will decrease as the level of the vehicle's automation and interconnection increases.

The different types of driving – from traditional to autonomous – are conventionally divided into five levels, depending on the driver's degree of involvement/responsibility. While in L1 CAV and partly in L2 CAV, drivers are wholly or partially liable for any harmful consequences and damages caused (except in cases of force majeure), at L3, 4 and 5, their liability progressively decreases until it disappears.

As stated by Lanzi (2021), the advent of self-driving vehicles will also involve a profound transformation in the traditional criminal responsibility for crimes caused by the circulation of the vehicles.

In fact, in the Italian legal system, by Constitutional provision (Article 27) criminal responsibility is personal and by reason of the provisions of Article 42 of the Italian Criminal Code, no action or omission envisaged by the law as a crime, if it has not been committed with conscience and will.

Consequently, if the person will therefore only be transported by the vehicle, in the absence of any legal obligation to supervise the vehicle itself, without any technical possibility to intervene on software choices and behaviours, he will not be attributable to any criminal liability. Otherwise, there will be at least an

obligation to supervise the person (as for L3 and 4 CAVs), in this case, he can still be considered a real driver or, at least, a vehicle operator.

The situation is slightly different in common law countries (UK, USA and former Commonwealth countries), where strict liability is commonly accepted, including in criminal law. It means that the operator/driver could be guilty of some traffic violations or vehicular crimes, even if he has not committed any violation or misconduct.

From the point of view of civil liability for damage caused by vehicle traffic, road accidents can cause very costly damages, liable drivers may not be able to pay relevant compensation. Consequently, in every country, drivers must take out a compulsory civil liability insurance policy. Besides, a Guarantee Fund has been set up to cover road casualties' compensation when no liable driver is identifiable, or the liable driver does not have a valid insurance policy.

However, this liability and guarantee system seems to no longer fully respond to the forthcoming and future semi-autonomous and autonomous driving scenarios. So, it must be gradually changed according to the different situations generated by the automation, which will replace human driving.

Even if the automated system is less prone to error, it cannot anticipate all situations, nor it has (yet) the typical human adaptive capacity of managing the unexpected events. Therefore, the system may misbehave or get stuck.

When driving does not mainly depend on the drivers' free choice, but on mechanisms that automatically work in line with standardized parameters defined by the vehicle and/or infrastructure manufacturers, it is essential to identify whether the automated system allows the drivers to resume driving promptly and independently – and if so, how.

If drivers cannot regain control of their vehicles due to causes not attributable to them (i.e., in case of what could be called a situational force majeure), the liability parameters change. Liability will no longer fall on the driver, but on the vehicle manufacturers and/or Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), maintenance service providers or the infrastructure managers.

In the Italian legal system, driving a vehicle is considered a complex activity with potentially dangerous effects, for this reason it is included in the extra-

contractual liability governed by Article 2050 of the Italian Civil Code, which provides that “Anyone who causes damage to others in carrying out a dangerous activity, by its nature or by the nature of the manoeuvre if it does not prove that it has adopted all suitable measures to avoid the damage” the vehicle and its driving are therefore considered as potentially dangerous due to the damage it can cause to people and things.

The first consequence is that, as foreseen in article 116 of the Italian Highway Code, to drive a motor vehicle (mopeds, motorcycles, tricycles, quadricycles, and motor vehicles) you must have obtained a driving license and, where required, professional qualifications. The driving license, compliant with the EU model, is distinguished in the categories provided for by European legislation. The other consequence is that, as foreseen in article 193 of the Italian Highway Code, motor vehicles without rails, cannot be placed on the road without insurance coverage in accordance with the current provisions of the law on civil liability towards third parties.

This provision is confirmed in article 122 of the legislative decree 07-09-2005, n. 209, the so-called Private Insurance Code, and it provides, as an obligatory condition for the circulation of vehicles, insurance for damages deriving from civil liability. This obligation responds to essentially two purposes: to guarantee the assets of the insured, against which the injured party could claim, and to protect the victims of accidents who might otherwise not be restored by an insolvent creditor. Furthermore, the Italian Code of Private Insurance provides for the operation, for insurance companies, of the obligation to contract this insurance guarantee named with the initials RCA.

At the origin of this obligation is the solidarity need to guarantee all vehicle owners adequate insurance coverage that can keep third parties harmless from the movement of vehicles. The Code identifies the minimum limits guaranteed in the event of a claim for damage to persons and property. There are also bonus or penalizing mechanisms, in terms of tariff premiums, directly related to the number of claims in which the insured is involved.

In Italy, autonomous driving is currently permitted only at the level of experimental driving and regulated by the Decree of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport called "Smart Road" of February 28, 2018 which,

in Article 19 states as follows:¹ The applicant must demonstrate that he has concluded the insurance contract for specific civil liability for the self-driving vehicle, pursuant to the law of 24 December 1969, n. 990, by depositing a copy with the authorizing subject, with a minimum ceiling equal to four times that envisaged for the vehicle used for the experimentation in its version without automatic driving technologies, according to current legislation.

The insurance contract expressly indicates that the insurer is aware of the methods of use of the vehicle and that the vehicle is used in automatic operating mode on public roads. In the UK, the legislation that regulates the obligations and main responsibilities for driving a motor vehicle is the Road Traffic Act of 1988, which, similarly to the regulations of most European countries, require a driving license (Article 164) and vehicle insurance (Article 143).

Unlike in Italy, however, in the UK, the regulation on driving autonomous vehicles did not stop at the discipline of the hypothesis of driving experimental vehicles and already in 2018, the Centre for Connected and Autonomous Vehicles asked the Law Commission of England and Wales and the Scottish Law Commission (together known as the "Joint Commission") to undertake a comprehensive review to enable the safe and responsible introduction of automated vehicles on British roads and public places.

By automated vehicles, the Centre for Connected and Autonomous Vehicles refer to vehicles that can drive themselves without being controlled or monitored by an individual for at least part of a journey. The legislative text called "Automated and Electric Vehicles Act 2018" completed the regulatory process, receiving the final consent (Royal Assent) last July 19, 2021. The text provides rules that apply to motor vehicles designed or adapted to be able, at least in some situations, to circulate autonomously in safety.

On this point, the British Ministry of Transport had however specified that most of the regulatory provisions would not come into force until the relative implementing regulations were introduced into the national legislative fabric; after all, autonomous vehicles were not expected to be in circulation on the UK road network before 2021, with further slippage partly generated by the economic crisis connected to the COVID 19 pandemic. After multiple rounds of

consultation, the Joint Commission published on January 26, 2022 the joint report (the "Report") with recommendations for legal reform¹.

2.1.2 Current situation of vehicle automation

Now, it's impossible to know whether in the future the automation systems will have to meet common standard type approval requirements, which it would be the best option in our opinion of trainers involved with the PAsCAL project, but it could also be partly proprietary. In the last case, vehicle manufacturers shall provide drivers with additional driving training, like it currently happens to vehicles equipped with the most Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS).

In particular, ADAS come in many forms: from systems that apply the brakes if they sense an imminent crash (Autonomous Emergency Braking) to ones that help maintain a constant distance from the car ahead (Adaptive Cruise Control) to others that help keep the vehicle in the lane (Lane Keep Assistance). (Thatcham, 2021).

The UK Law Commission (2022) report of 26th January 2022 also proposes a common standardisation process of automated vehicles: "We therefore recommend a new "authorisation" scheme to decide whether any given ADS feature is or is not self-driving as a matter of law. This will distinguish between good (possibly very good) driver assistance features and those which are safe enough to allow the vehicle to drive itself".

With the deployment of highly or fully automated driving systems, scenarios would change. Currently, it's possible only to envisage focusing driver training on different skills and management of critical situations, just like in training of high-speed train drivers or airplane pilots.

When considering the future driver training needs as new and higher levels of autonomy arrive on the market a crucial element to consider is the need for the driver to interact with the on-board systems and be ready to 'take over' control.

First, it's necessary to consider that drivers must learn to check that all the interaction systems between the vehicle, road and any central connection (e.g.,

¹ <https://www.lawcom.gov.uk/project/automated-vehicles>

the 5G network) are properly working. This step is essential to activating highly automated or autonomous driving modes. Training includes monitoring the alerts (e.g., acoustic or visual) and how to re-take control of the car in case of disconnection or malfunctioning of the systems, allowing drivers to smoothly pull over to ensure the safety of any passengers and road users.

To tackle the Driver Take Over control procedure challenge, an innovative system was proposed by the Human Factors Research Group from the University of Nottingham (Shaw, Large and Burnett, 2020). It will be considered later in the training modules development.

2.1.3 General approach of the training methodology

WP5 focuses on the definition of a didactic methodology regarding CAV levels 3 and 4 driving, targeting the different categories of drivers foreseen, i.e., novice drivers, experienced drivers and professional drivers and trainers.

This methodology was drawn up based on the experiences and observations made through the use of the HSS driving simulator, through the review of research already carried out and the teaching experiences already gained over the years by the teachers / instructors of the driving schools belonging to the ACI networks, Ready2Go (Italy) and RED (England).

The HSS requirements definition (see Deliverable D 5.1) identified some potentially critical situations for the self-driving systems of L3 and 4 CAVs. In particular, two operating settings have been designed, one Urban and one Motorway, to be faced with two different levels of automation, in 2 autonomous driving modes, ECO or SPORT.

During the Beta testing phase of the HSS, while the development of the HSS was still ongoing, a trial test phase was undertaken by analysing the behaviours of the Trainers and collecting their observations on the different scenarios faced with the different autonomous driving modes available.

Hence the opportunity, in a preliminary analysis phase, to combine the different categories of drivers into two macro profiles: Experienced Driver (sub categorised as: experienced drivers, professional drivers and trainers) and Novice Driver.

2.2 Theoretical modules for all types of drivers

The approach taken within this section reflects that all levels of driving ability will require some form of driver training related to CAVs. The modules proposed within this report are laid out in general terms and should always be considered in line with the local laws and common driver training policies of each member country.

2.2.1 Theoretical modules taking into account the UK context

In the frame of the ongoing work within WP5, RDS considered that their existing learner driver training syllabus, made up of some 22 individual theoretical training modules, would require an urgent update to address a lack of content regarding the training of existing ADAS systems.

Work was started to introduce and develop new content to address the missing theoretical elements for ADAS systems with a view to using this new content within a sub-module of the existing training module for ‘Controlling the vehicle’. This new sub-module would also prepare content related to the higher CAV levels as they become available. It was essential to consider incorporating much of the learnings from activities within the PAsCAL project across all theoretical training modules which make up the learning to drive syllabus (UK). By integrating CAV training across all 22 modules of the syllabus this could best influence novice drivers understanding and acceptance of CAVs from the beginning; whilst the new sub-module content aimed specifically at training ADAS systems, can also be used separately for the training of experienced and professional drivers.

All content within the ‘RED (UK) Complete learning to drive syllabus with theory and practical matrix V1 Feb 2nd, 2022’ (see appendix 5.3) is drafted in line with the UK regulator document National Standard for Driver and Rider Training (Driver and Vehicle Standards Agency, 2020).

A short description of the new content to be added within the syllabus follows:

Module Component		<i>Understanding of CAV related concepts</i>		
Short Description		An introduction to the levels of autonomy as per the SAE guide. Levels 0 - 5 explained with emphasis on levels 2, 3, and 4, in particular - driver assistance features are covered in detail.		
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
Competency/skills		<p>List of competencies covered from D5.1</p> <p>1 Knowledge of the capability and competence of the CAV</p> <p>2 Knowledge of automation procedures</p> <p>3 Knowledge of what is the purpose of each technology of the CAV</p> <p>4 Knowledge of the limitations and possible failure of the CAV technologies</p> <p>5 Knowledge of the legal constraints/traffic laws related to the driving of the CAV</p> <p>6 Supervise the CAV autonomous technology works well</p> <p>7 Knowledge of the practical implications of being In the Loop, On the Loop and Out of The Loop</p>		

Details of the sub-sections and how they fit to the competencies identified in the Deliverable 5.1 are briefly described below:

1. Knowledge of the capability and competence of the CAV
2. Knowledge of automation procedures
3. Knowledge of what is the purpose of each technology of the CAV
4. Knowledge of the limitations and possible failure of the CAV technologies

Training module includes:

- a) knowledge of the levels of driving automation and typical features anticipated within each level. This includes training on how the driver can continue their learning as new technology is introduced. Charts as in figure 1 below, will help drivers to visualise the difference between CAV levels.

SAE J3016™ LEVELS OF DRIVING AUTOMATION™
Learn more here: sae.org/standards/content/j3016_202104

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	SAE LEVEL 0™	SAE LEVEL 1™	SAE LEVEL 2™	SAE LEVEL 3™	SAE LEVEL 4™	SAE LEVEL 5™
What does the human in the driver's seat have to do?	You are driving whenever these driver support features are engaged – even if your feet are off the pedals and you are not steering			You are not driving when these automated driving features are engaged – even if you are seated in “the driver's seat”		
	You must constantly supervise these support features; you must steer, brake or accelerate as needed to maintain safety			When the feature requests, you must drive	These automated driving features will not require you to take over driving	
Copyright © 2021 SAE International.						
What do these features do?	These are driver support features			These are automated driving features		
	These features are limited to providing warnings and momentary assistance	These features provide steering OR brake/acceleration support to the driver	These features provide steering AND brake/acceleration support to the driver	These features can drive the vehicle under limited conditions and will not operate unless all required conditions are met		This feature can drive the vehicle under all conditions
Example Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • automatic emergency braking • blind spot warning • lane departure warning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lane centering OR • adaptive cruise control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lane centering AND • adaptive cruise control at the same time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • traffic jam chauffeur 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • local driverless taxi • pedals/steering wheel may or may not be installed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • same as level 4, but feature can drive everywhere in all conditions

Figure 1 SAE Levels of driving automation training aid (SAE, 2019)

- b) Knowledge of CAV capabilities (including ADAS) and their limitations. An important element within the training is to cover in depth the capabilities and limitations of each CAV level. New driver behavioural e-learning training tool will be commissioned as part of RED's work within WP9.

5. Knowledge of the legal constraints/traffic laws related to the driving of the CAV

Training module includes:

Training in awareness of Motorway Code rules and regulations related to the safe use of CAVs, for all types of drivers, to ensure not just compliance with the rules and regulations, but a wider understanding of the responsibilities associated with being a driver of higher level CAVs.

Note: this section will require an update pending UK Law Commission recommendations on the definition of ‘user in charge’

of automated vehicles being adopted into law by the UK government (UK Law Commission, 2022).

6. Supervise the CAV autonomous technology works well

7. Knowledge of the practical implications of being In the Loop, On the Loop and Out of The Loop

Training module includes:

- a) Driver training in how to use the 'Take-Back' recommended control procedure or CHAT - CHeck, Assess and Takeover - (Shaw et al. 2020) considering analysis of critical situations and the potential for other unforeseen developments to occur.

RED driving schools have adopted this recommended procedure into their training materials as shown in figure 2 below. This procedure is a visual aid to trainers describing how the procedure will work to drivers undergoing training.

Figure 2 A typical visual aid to trainers introducing the CHAT procedure (Shaw et al., 2020)

- b) Training will be provided in understanding the term 'transition training' and the acknowledgment of the responsibility of the driver when upskilling to higher levels of autonomous driving. This section recognises that most drivers will go through a transition period, i.e., experiencing driving within lower levels of CAV prior to upskilling and transitioning to a CAV L3 or L4 vehicle. This section aims to

equip the driver with the necessary process to safely upskill to the next CAV level. A new driver behavioural e-learning training tool will be commissioned as part of RED's work within PAsCAL WP9 and then retrospectively added to this module.

Applicable to all competencies

Training module includes:

a) Driver approach to autonomous driving when entering and using a CAV best practice guide provided during training and is covered using training materials within the module, an example is shown below figure 3, a slide taken directly from the presentation.

Figure 3 A slide from the presentation intended to cover the best practice guide to driver approach

For the latest updates and guidance about the UK CAVs vision, see the Centre for connected and autonomous vehicles website².

Recommendation

² <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/centre-for-connected-and-autonomous-vehicles>

RDS recognise the potential benefit to the ‘optimal cognitive workload’ (i.e., low but not too low) of the driver by linking the theoretical modules and driver wellbeing training together to target a positive driver attitude towards automation and the CAV, whilst maintaining the benefits of continuing to train the “old” procedural skills/competencies as described in Deliverable D5.1.

As a reminder, in addition to “hard competencies”, D5.1 highlights several variables and “softer elements” to consider when aiming safety driving (see figure 4 below).

Figure 4 The CAV cognitive and affective model suggested in D5.1

RDS have an existing 4-module program targeting driver wellbeing which covers topics such as “Resiliency”, “Fatigue”, “Nutrition, exercise and hydration”, and “Emotions”.

A brief description of these Driver Wellbeing modules follows highlighting how they link to the competencies in Deliverable 5.1 directly.

Module Component		Driver Wellbeing and Resiliency – How your heart rules your head!		
Short Description		Webinar based interactive presentation designed to engage candidates with thinking about how their own wellbeing can influence day to day and task-based decisions they make. Learning some simple tips to help manage daily stresses and anxiety caused during the task of driving which equally relates to interaction with automated driving.		
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
Competency/skills		<p>List of competencies covered from D5.1</p> <p>11 Maintaining fitness to drive during automated driving</p> <p>12 Check yourself (ready to drive, fit, non-driving task stopped, hands free, comfy chair position and ready to use steering wheel and pedals)</p> <p>17 Assess the situation and the next step you will do</p> <p>Cognitive and affective states management (low cognitive workload, low cognitive fatigue, high situation awareness, few distractions, neutral valence and balanced arousal)</p>		

Its content is accessible at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sUvyzmpVS6Eandt=9s>

Module Component		Fatigue - Recharging and the importance of sleep		
Short Description		Webinar based interactive presentation designed to engage candidates with thinking about how their own wellbeing can influence day to day and task-based decisions they make. Learning some simple tips to help manage their sleep patterns to aid driver performance and reduce the risk of falling asleep at the wheel or being inattentive during periods of low interaction with the task of driving, for example during periods that any automated systems are operational.		
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
Competency/skills		<p>List of competencies covered from D5.1</p> <p>11 Maintaining fitness to drive during automated driving</p> <p>12 Check yourself (ready to drive, fit, non-driving task stopped, hands free, comfy chair position and ready to use steering wheel and pedals)</p> <p>17 Assess the situation and the next step you will do</p> <p>19 Supervise the CAV to be ready to take back control</p> <p>Cognitive and affective states management (low cognitive workload, low cognitive fatigue, high situation awareness, few distractions, neutral valence and balanced arousal)</p>		

Its content is accessible at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s4AqgoxDTYo>

Module Component		Nutrition, exercise and hydration – How to fuel for success		
Short Description		Webinar based interactive presentation designed to engage candidates with thinking about how their own wellbeing can influence day to day and task-based decisions they make. Learning some simple tips to help manage their nutrition, exercise and hydration routines to aid driver performance and reduce the risk of distraction whilst in control of a vehicle.		
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
Competency/skills		<p>List of competencies covered from D5.1</p> <p>11 Maintaining fitness to drive during automated driving</p> <p>12 Check yourself (ready to drive, fit, non-driving task stopped, hands free, comfy chair position and ready to use steering wheel and pedals)</p> <p>14 Check for hazards during manual and autonomous mode</p> <p>17 Assess the situation and the next step you will do</p> <p>19 Supervise the CAV to be ready to take back control</p> <p>Cognitive and affective states management (low cognitive workload, low cognitive fatigue, high situation awareness, few distractions, neutral valence and balanced arousal)</p>		

Its content is accessible at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4lYjZRnpCyEandt=34s>

Module Component		Control your emotions - Pass it on for a higher pass rate		
Short Description		Webinar based interactive presentation designed to engage candidates with thinking about how their own wellbeing can influence day to day and task-based decisions they make. Bringing together the learnings from the earlier modules to better understand how all the tips can help you control your emotions better, and how they link to future success, whether that be an upcoming driving test or mandatory training. Candidates are also encouraged to pass on tips they have learnt from attending the presentations to family and friends.		
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
Competency/skills		<p>List of competencies covered from D5.1</p> <p>11 Maintaining fitness to drive during automated driving</p> <p>12 Check yourself (ready to drive, fit, non-driving task stopped, hands free, comfy chair position and ready to use steering wheel and pedals)</p> <p>17 Assess the situation and the next step you will do</p> <p>19 Supervise the CAV to be ready to take back control</p> <p>Cognitive and affective states management (low cognitive workload, low cognitive fatigue, high situation awareness, few distractions, neutral valence and balanced arousal)</p>		

Its content is accessible at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wf66u5dKM1sandt=18s>

Notes about UK Regulations

There is no specific definition of “drive” or “driving” in the UK Road Traffic Act (1988) but section 192(1) considers that a “driver, where a separate person acts as a steersman of a motor vehicle, includes (except for the purposes of section 1 of this Act) that person as well as any other person engaged in the driving of the vehicle, and “drive” is to be interpreted accordingly”.

Further relevant guidance from the UK government can be found within the ‘Code of Practice: automated vehicle trialling’, updated in January 2022, which states:

“As part of complying with the law, they will need to ensure that they have: a driver or operator, in or out of the vehicle, who is ready, able, and willing to resume control of the vehicle and have appropriate insurance in place”.

This guidance provides some insight into how the UK government may interpret the future role of ‘driver’ within a CAV ready environment.

Of particular interest within this code, is the provision for a driver to be deemed equal under the law whether they be ‘in or out of the vehicle’ The code goes on to state: “During trials, it is a legal requirement that there is a safety driver or safety operator ready and able to override the vehicle, though not necessarily within the vehicle.”

The question then arises that if the ‘driver’ is out of the vehicle, i.e., the vehicle is being driven remotely as in the trial described in a recent article (Autoexpress, 2021).

Then how should a driver of a lesser level CAV, interact safely with this vehicle if they are unable to read the others intention as there is no traditional ‘driver’ on board?

Given these UK based trials have or soon will start, we consider this question requires urgent further study and it may result in the above training modules requiring an update, or a new training sub-module being required completely.

2.2.2 Theoretical modules taking into account the Italian context

Regarding the Italian Law, ACI highlights that according to the current legislation it is not possible to apply an e-learning teaching system as it is prohibited by the ministerial decree 317/95.

ACI proposes the following modules to be provided in driving schools for all types of drivers:

Module Component		The 6 Levels of Autonomous Driving		
Short Description		An introduction to the levels of autonomy as per the SAE guide. Levels 0 - 5 explained with emphasis on levels 2, 3, and 4, in particular - driver assistance features such as ADAS are covered in detail.		
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
Competency/skills		List of competencies covered from D5.1 1 Knowledge of the capability and competence of the CAV		
		✓ Trainers		

Details of the content are described below:

- Description of the 6 levels of autonomous driving with technical and regulatory references with respect to real use and references to the tests that will subsequently be carried out on the simulator.

This takes into account the definition (see figure 5 below) of autonomous driving levels (SAE, 2019) detailed below.

Figure 5 SAE Levels of driving automation (SAE, 2019)

Level 0: concerns the warning systems, i.e., those systems that do not intervene directly on the driving of the vehicle but warn the driver with acoustic or visual signals of the detected situation suggesting the operations to be carried out (e.g., Lane Keeping Warning).

Level 1: it includes those systems that can intervene in driving in the event of a potentially dangerous situation that requires activation. In this case the system intervenes automatically through actions on the steering (e.g., Lane Keeping Assist), causing the vehicle to accelerate or decelerate (e.g., Emergency Brake Assist).

Level 2: the systems that assist the driver in ordinary driving activities with levels of automation such as to carry out driving functions both in the longitudinal and lateral direction (steering), so they do not intervene in particular situations but can always be present while driving (e.g., Adaptive Cruise Control) and must be activated at the beginning of the journey.

Level 3: The third level of automation corresponds to highly automated driving. Unlike levels 1 and 2, the vehicle takes full control through the automatic use of the accelerator, brake and steering (assisted by all the Adas already

provided in level 1 and 2) in specific situations, without the driver being required to intervene. In level 3, the driver must always be in a position to fully regain driving control when the system prompts him to do so, with sufficient notice, or when the driver himself deems it appropriate to regain control of the vehicle.

It is important to underline that the moment of resuming control, as indicated by the car, is complex and critical.

The first level 3 autonomous driving systems are likely to enter the European market in 2022, with Germany being the first country to grant approval for level 3 driving on certain roads, in managed conditions, namely drivers will only be able to activate the technology in slow-moving traffic on the motorway at speeds of up to 60km/h)³. The UK Law Commission (2022) published its findings into automated vehicles on 26 January 2022. The UK government has yet to adopt the recommendations.

Level 4: This level of automation corresponds to fully automated driving, in which the system assumes full management of the vehicle, automatically addressing all the related situations and requiring the driver to resume the commands should the system not be able to manage the critical situation detected. Compared to level 3, the driver cannot resume the controls at his sole discretion, but the car will decide if and when.

Level 5: it is a 100% autonomous car with driverless driving. The vehicle therefore takes full control of driving from departure to arrival without the need for human corrective interventions and in which all vehicle occupants are considered mere passengers (no driver or supervisor). Vehicles in road traffic interact with each other and exchange data with each other. The CAV 5, due to its peculiarities, will represent an excellent solution for people with reduced mobility such as the disabled, the elderly or children.

According to the provisions therefore, for levels up to 4, the driver is called into question and must be able to intervene where necessary.

³ <https://www.ashurst.com/-/media/ashurst/documents/news-and-insights/legal-updates/2021/aug/in-pole-position.pdf>.

Only with level 5 will we no longer have a driver inside the vehicle, who will be able to independently manage any condition, but to achieve the latest level of automation, as well as an important development of driving systems automated, it will also require a large investment in infrastructure as well as full connection between roads, vehicles and other types of road users.

Remark: Figure 5 above is the official representation of levels of driving automation from SAE. A visual alternative⁴ that can provide a simpler understanding is proposed at figure 6 below.

Figure 6 Visual alternative for levels of driving automation

4

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339371847/figure/fig1/AS:860500187422722@1582170640975/SAE-J3016-levels-of-driving-automation.png>

Module Component		Legal perspectives of the driver responsibility using a CAV		
Short Description		Awareness of civil and criminal liability during the use of CAVs		
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
Competency/skills		List of competencies covered from D5.1 1 Knowledge of the capability and competence of the CAV 2 Knowledge of automation procedures 4 Knowledge of the legal constraints/traffic laws related to the driving of the CAV		

Details of the content are described below:

Awareness of the position drivers hold with respect to any civil and criminal liability is based on notes related to:

- Some following regulatory references: Directive 2010/40 / EU, Directive 85/374 / Cee, DM 70/2018 Legislative Decree 206/2005.
- The definition of the driver's level of responsibility.

More than 52 years after the signing of the Vienna Convention on road traffic (1968), we are becoming more and more aware of how much it was necessary, then as now, both to meet the needs of road safety, and to facilitate the development of autonomous and / or automated driving systems through above all the additions made over the years such as: modification of the Acc. of 1 May. 1971 completing the Convention (RS 0.741.101, annex 7) and the amendments of 26 March. 2014, effective 23rd March 2016 (AS 2016 1019).

Of the aforementioned Convention, among the general principles, great attention should be paid to Chapter 1 Art 8 which describes the figure of the driver.

In paragraph 1, it is established, that a moving vehicle must always have a driver and that each driver must have constant control of his vehicle, specifying then, in paragraph 5, that the driver of a vehicle must refrain from any activity other than driving, to continue with paragraph 5bis, 6 and 13 in which, although no explicit reference is made to the on-board systems of the cars that allow automated or autonomous driving, they do however refer to the principle of responsibility of the driver expressed in Article 5. In the first paragraph of Article 13, for example, it is stated that: "Every driver of a vehicle must, under all circumstances, remain in control of his vehicle in order to be able to comply with the requirements of prudence and to be constantly able to carry out all the manoeuvres that belong to him".

Already these articles are sufficient to establish that the role of the driver must be very different from the passenger who is free to be distracted and to carry out any activity on a L3 or 4 CAV.

Going into the individual legislations of the signatory states, article 10 of the Decree of 28 February 2018, of the Italian Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, which leaves little room for interpretation by providing for the figure of the "supervisor" that is the occupant of the vehicle, on the driver's side, who must always be able to take control of the vehicle independently by the degree of automation of the same, at any time if the need arises, by acting on the vehicle controls in absolute precedence on the automated systems and which, therefore, is the person responsible for the circulation of the vehicle. When he takes actual driving, in manual mode, he takes on the role of driver. In fact, there is no difference between the figure of the supervisor and the driver because in order to be able to take the controls of a vehicle and be able to drive it, you must be in possession of the qualifications (driving license).

In light of this regulatory framework, when a CAV circulates on public roads, a driver must be on board, able to take control the vehicle if needed.

The CAV raises several legal questions that are not simple to answer: in the event of an accident, will the owner, driver, vehicle manufacturer or software programmer be responsible?

The rules applicable from a civil point of view in the event of an accident involving a L3 or 4 vehicle make both the owner and the user, the only user,

the driver and the owner responsible and, albeit indirectly, the manufacturer (for production or maintenance defects). As regards the criminal liability connected to an accident is actually the person responsible is always the driver (or supervisor) who incurs the already provided ancillary sanctions of withdrawal, suspension, revision or revocation of the driving license according to the seriousness of the offenses committed.

This legislation, in hindsight, will see a change only when the circulation of L5 CAVs is allowed, not only to establish who will be liable for civil and criminal liability (in the event of an accident, the question will probably arise as to whether the accident has occurred for an error in the evaluation of the autopilot or for a programmer error that did not take into account all the variables and, ultimately, the error of the owner due to lack of maintenance or tampering), in consideration of the fact that the occupant of the vehicle will no longer be a supervisor or driver.

Module Component	The CAV capabilities (Advanced Driver-Assistance systems) and their limitations			
Short Description	An overview of the automated technologies that assist drivers in driving and parking functions			
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
			✓	Trainers
Competency/skills	List of competencies covered from D5.1 1 Knowledge or the capability and competence of the CAV 2 Knowledge of automation procedures 3 Knowledge of what is the purpose of each technology of the CAV 4. Knowledge of the limitations and possible failure of the CAV technologies			

Details of the content are described below.

ADAS are driving assistance systems, designed to improve vehicle performance and today increasingly widespread on the market. They can be presented with non-uniform terminology, while actually indicating the same functionality, or still included in packages commercial vehicles that can group different types with a single name (e.g., Dynamic Chassis Control, IntelliSafe assist, Active Safety Pack, Safety Sense, Driving Assistant...).

How they are classified by ERSO, SAE AND BOSH?

We have always called them SAS: Active Security Systems. SAE places them in the first 3 levels of the VGA class; ERSO (European Road Safety Observatory) divides them into two classes: "Known effects on safety" and "Unknown effects on safety."

- the first class includes those systems whose effects on safety are known,
- the second class includes those devices whose impacts have not yet been clearly quantified,

Why study ADAS systems within a project that looks to the future of automated driving?

Current ADAS represent the maximum technology available on-board today's cars and are the foundation of L3 CAVs.

To be a CAV's safe driver therefore, it is considered necessary by trainers that drivers have to master ADAS systems.

The functioning of the main driving aid systems currently on the market are detailed below, namely:

1. Adaptive cruise control
2. Automatic emergency braking
3. Parking sensors
4. Lane change warning
5. Automatic recognition and reading of signals
6. Intelligent speed adaptation (ISAs)
7. Automatic recognition of obstacles and pedestrians
8. Event recording system in case of accidents
9. Drowsiness and attention level detection
10. Tire pressure monitoring system
11. User visual improvement and blind spot elimination (Blis)
12. Notes on the classic Adas ABS ESC exception
13. Outline of the 3rd Mobility Package containing the Lifesaving Package published by the European Commission

Most of the common Adas are displayed in the figure 7 below.

Figure 7 ADAS systems (Electronicanews, 2018)

The main novelty of this theoretical part seeks to stimulate the student to ask himself a simple question: how is a car made and how does it work? This module is in fact a sort of journey "inside" this mysterious machine, illustrating with a simple and clear language what ADAS are and how they work and when they come into operation.

Understanding broadly how the devices works helps the driving candidate to use his car in the best way, both from a functional point of view (use and maintenance) and from a greater driving safety.

The formulation was also designed to be an adequate support for preparing for the exam and for the practical test.

ACC - Adaptive Cruise Control is a Cruise speed control system which automatically adjusts the speed by means of radar or laser detection while maintaining a safe distance from the vehicles in front.

This type of device is able to change the pace according to traffic conditions. Adaptive Cruise Control is an extension of Cruise Control; allows the vehicle to accelerate or brake autonomously without the need for the intervention of the driver if there is an obstacle in front of the vehicle. Unlike Cruise Control, Adaptive Cruise Control provides, in addition to setting the desired cruise speed, also for entering the distance you want to keep from the vehicle in front. You can choose whether to leave more or less space between our car and the one in front, always maintaining safety standards based on speed. The ACC reacts only to moving and stopping objects moving in the same direction as the vehicle.

It does not react to stationary objects or objects coming towards the vehicle. An object that is initially recognized as moving and then stops is classified as a stopped object. Example: ACC checks the distance to a moving vehicle in front. In the event of approaching a red traffic light, the vehicle in front brakes until it stops. At this point the object is classified as stopped.

The ACC reacts accordingly to this object and continues to apply the distance adjustment. An object that has not so far been recognized as moving is classified as stationary. Example: The ACC approaches a red traffic light,

where there are already stationary vehicles. For this reason, the ACC does not react with respect to these vehicles.

This measure is necessary to prevent the ACC from reacting to non-relevant stationary objects, such as signs, manholes or bridges. The ACC function is specific to a speed range, as a rule, from 5 km / h to 125 km / h. Above or below this threshold value, the active ACC is automatically deactivated, irrespective of the driver's request. To control the distance to a vehicle in front, ACC limits the engine torque required by the Cruise Control and controls the retarder (depending on the version and availability) and the wheel brakes. For this reason, ACC cannot normally accelerate a vehicle by itself. The drive torque for acceleration is only required by Cruise Control.

In some models, ACC has been integrated with secondary functions. It is interesting, for example, that the cruise control can automatically adapt to the limits in force, which the car itself reads by interpreting the vertical signs through the camera located behind the windshield.

Some ACCs are able to communicate with the GPS and predict what type of route you are about to tackle. Thus, if they notice that there is a series of tight corners in front of the car, ACC automatically begins to reduce speed so as not to force the driver to brake abruptly. Similarly, if the cruise control detects that you are about to tackle a climb, then it will seek some momentum to tackle the slope with less effort from the engine.

In many vehicles equipped with automatic transmission, ACC could modify the cruising speed by also changing the ratio and making the engine always work at maximum torque speeds. The system is also able to bring the car to a complete stop and zero speed.

The column running function, in fact, allows you to stop the vehicle completely when you are in the queue (also switching off the engine thanks to Stop and Start) and to restart automatically as soon as the vehicle in front of ours starts moving again.

ACC limitations: the device shows variable performance in terms of effectiveness when approaching stationary vehicles and in the management of

road gradients and / or curves where it loses "coupling" to previous vehicles. Particularly relevant is the problem of "false positives and / or false alarms" that derive from incorrect identification of obstacles, which do not actually exist (example: a vehicle returning from overtaking, shadows of billboards on the carriageway etc), which activate emergency with high risk of rear-end collision by following vehicles.

This raises the question of acceptance of higher levels of autonomy with drivers who may have used ACC and be put off due to its limitations. This could negatively impact on their view towards accepting and engaging with higher levels of autonomy as they become available. For this reason, it is necessary to ensure during training that limitations of ADAS systems such as ACC are fully explored to ensure adoption and use of ADAS systems to persuade experienced drivers that advancement in CAV level of technology is a positive. The proposed training modules content cover this aspect in detail and will help improve acceptance of ADAS systems in general, but CAVs in particular (see appendix 5.1).

ABS – The Anti-lock braking system is an anti-lock system of the wheels, mandatory since 2004 on all cars on the market. The system allows, thanks to a series of sensors located on the wheels of the car and connected to a control unit, to prevent the wheels from locking following sudden braking. The control unit reads the speed of each of the four wheels of the vehicle and, when it detects the blocking of one or more of the latter following a sudden stop by the driver, it intervenes on the hydraulic pump, regulating the braking force to be applied in the most correct way. on each of them, thus managing to prevent the car from skidding. ABS is particularly effective, for example, in situations where driving is made difficult by adverse weather conditions (rain, ice, etc.).

ESC - Electronic Stability Control system, was made mandatory in all newly homologated vehicles starting from 2011, while for those newly registered, but homologated before 2011, from 2014. The system enters in operation to prevent the vehicle from skidding when, for example, the driver takes a bend incorrectly, or loses control of the vehicle and finds himself having to manage a sudden and unwanted change of trajectory. The device acts in a combined

manner with ABS and with the TSC (Traction Control System Electronic Vehicle Traction Control, anti-skid or anti-skid, which has the function of reactivating the grip between tires and road pavement), reducing the power of the engine and braking the wheels directly, also by dosing the force on each of them differently.

ISA - Intelligent Speed Adaptation supports the driver in respecting the speed limits present along the route and includes information on the speed limit referring to the road section you are traveling on, integrating it with an audio and video signal that warns the driver of any exceeding of the limit (Warning ISA), or by acting on the accelerator pedal (Assisting ISA) or on fuel injection (Restricting ISA) to induce driver behaviour to comply with permitted limits.

ISA allows you to recognize road signs through a special camera (or by detecting the position via GPS) and in some vehicles this system is combined with Adaptive Cruise Control. It is therefore a system that supports the driver in respecting the speed limits present along the route.

AEB - Emergency Brake Assist: applies automatic braking in the event of a potential collision with vehicles moving in front, with the aim of reducing stopping time and distance, supporting the driver which tends to apply pressure to the brake which is not adequate for the emergency condition.

The Advanced Emergency Braking System (AEBS) is a system that can automatically detect a potential frontal collision and activate the vehicle's braking system to decelerate the vehicle for the purpose of avoiding or mitigating a collision. Once an impending collision, these systems provide a warning to the driver. When a collision becomes imminent, they can act autonomously without any intervention from the driver (braking, steering or both). Collision avoidance by braking is appropriate at low vehicle speeds (e.g., below 50 km / h), while collision avoidance by steering may be more appropriate at higher vehicle speeds if the lanes are clear. Cars with collision avoidance can also be equipped with Adaptive Cruise Control, using the same sensors that look forward. In the near future, automatic emergency braking will also combine with the recognition of cyclists and pedestrians, which already exists on the market on some car models. A sensor generally mounted above the windshield constantly detects the distance from the vehicle in front of us,

using a radar or a light refraction system. If the control unit, using information on speed and trajectory, determines that the collision is close, then it warns the driver and preloads the braking system. If the collision is imminent and there are still no reactions from the side of the driver, apply the brakes. Depending on the model, the system may be deactivated if the driver brakes with sufficient force or if the line changes.

City-AEB - Autonomous emergency braking systems detects, through on-board sensors, vehicles, or other road users in the vicinity of the vehicle itself and, in cases identified as "risk of collision", applies emergency braking to avoid the accident or in any case to reduce its impact. The systems commonly referred to as "City-AEB" or "low speed AEB" are capable of braking to avoid a collision at a relative speed of approximately 15 km / h.

Forward Collision Warning: through audio and video messages it warns when a vehicle is too close to the one in front, considering the measured speeds of the vehicles.

ATTENTION: it may be difficult to identify obstacles and / or pedestrians in the event of poor visibility or obstructed by other vehicles, perhaps parked, or objects. Same problem of "false positives" described in the previous Adas.

Reverse Collision Warning System: with audio and video messages, it intervenes when a vehicle is too close to a rear obstacle, detected by sensors placed in the bumper.

Difference between AEB and FCW

AEB (Autonomous Emergency Braking) is different from FCW (Forward Collision Warning): FCW warns the driver but does not apply the vehicle's brakes by itself. The AEB has three characteristics: Range: the system acts independently of the driver to avoid or mitigate the accident.

Emergency: the system will only intervene in a critical situation.

Braking: the system tries to avoid the accident by applying the brakes.

Time to collision could be a way to choose the most appropriate prevention method (braking or steering).

The steering collision avoidance system is a new concept. However, the steering collision avoidance system has some limitations: excessive dependence on lane markings, limitations of sensors and interaction between the driver and the system. Sensors and cameras: assist the driver in parking or reversing; in the most advanced devices, the on-board computer also takes care of carrying out the manoeuvres, turning the steering wheel and operating the brake and accelerator. It is a device consisting of sensors positioned on the front and rear bumpers that emit ultrasonic waves when they intercept the nearest obstacle, sending information to an electronic board. The parking sensors are hidden in the vehicle's bumpers, so as not to affect the design of the car, and at the moment of the manoeuvre they emit an acoustic signal that becomes greater or more insistent as you approach the obstacle. Parking sensors have evolved over time to become one of the most advanced driver assistance systems.

ATTENTION: The system may encounter problems in identifying pedestrians and / or vehicles, especially at night, in particular weather conditions and in blind turns to the right. Activation of braking without reason.

KLA - LDW - Lane Keeping Warning Devices: they warn when the on-board sensors detect that the vehicle is not correctly maintaining its lane. Since this is only a warning signal, the impact on safety also depends on the driver's reaction and on the good visibility of road markings.

Lane Assist is the driving assistance system that warns the distracted driver when the line that delimits his lane is crossed. The lane maintenance system, like most ADAS, supports the driver, but it does not replace it. It is therefore good to keep in mind that, when driving, attention and concentration must remain high and hands firmly on the wheel. The system, based on the processing of the images detected by a vision device, can identify and

recognize the demarcation lines painted on the carriageway. The images processed by specific software make it possible to alert the driver if the vehicle approaches the line excessively or risks crossing them. Lane Assist uses a camera, located behind the windshield (usually at the rear of the interior rear-view mirror), to monitor road markings.

It is a system that uses a forward-facing camera to detect the boundary line of the carriageway, warning the driver if the vehicle leaves the lane without using the direction indicator correctly.

How is lane assist activated? Each car has its own (COMMAND) button to operate Lane Assist. Just press it to turn it on or off. How the lane keeping system works. These are the warning lights that tell the driver whether the system is active or not. Normally, when activated, it is possible to find yourself in one of the following situations: an optical and acoustic warning with which the system warns the driver that the boundary lines of the carriageway or lane have been crossed; if the driver has the direction indicators on, or suddenly releases the accelerator pedal or brakes, the system is deactivated. Vibrations on the steering wheel or seat with which the system warns the driver that he does not have both hands on the steering wheel; If the direction indicators are not activated and the vehicle crosses the boundary lines of the carriageway or lane, the system corrects the trajectory automatically returning the vehicle to its lane. The system reacts with a counter-steering impulse and a vibration of the steering wheel to warn the driver of the approach of another car and the consequent danger. The system, if necessary, is capable of counter-steering. The system is capable of operating even in the dark or in the event of fog, but only within the limits allowed by the visibility offered by the headlights and the characteristics of the camera.

In these cases, in fact, the lane keeping system warns that operation may be limited. In addition, Lane Assist does not function when switching from active to fault mode when the lane markings are indistinguishable, if it does not detect your hands on the steering wheel and in the event of an excessively tight corner. There are various types of Lane Assist. Each manufacturer attributes to this type of ADAS different names and acronyms, which can often be confusing and disorienting, such as Lane Keeping Aid, Active Lane Assist or

Lane Assistant. The intrinsic meaning does not change, each of these offers the same operation, that is to assist the driver in maintaining the trajectory.

ATTENTION: Although very useful in preventing accidents where the driver could jump lanes due to distraction, it requires the driver to make a lane change with all the necessary attention (example: using the direction indicators) in order not to fall into a momentary behaviour of the vehicle that hinders crossing the centre line (or lane).

TSR – Traffic Sign Recognition " Recognition of Road Signs " is a driver assistance system that recognizes vertical road signs by means of a multifunctional camera (the same used by LANE ASSIST). The signs, and in particular the speed limits, are highlighted on the dashboard for the attention of the driver. If the camera cannot read the road sign, the limit will be indicated on the dashboard or on the navigator using the data stored in the navigation system. Depending on the technology used by the vehicle manufacturer, the system can limit itself to flashing the speed indicator on the instrument panel display accompanied by an acoustic warning if the limits set are exceeded or it can interact with the Adaptive Cruise Control and adjust autonomously the speed based on the readings of the speed limit signs. The camera, used for the TSR, also allows for the integration of a wide range of driver assistance functions, to improve safety on board, to satisfy all the needs of the driver.

Warning of the presence of pedestrians, emergency braking and lane keeping. If the system uses an infrared camera, it can work even in case of poor visibility.

ATTENTION: To function correctly, this system requires signs positioned correctly, not hidden by vegetation or other obstructions and must be precise; in the case of using the Adas Isa, for example, if a speed limit is not set, the vehicle will continue to not exceed the limit previously imposed.

PDS - These are systems that through sensors and cameras detect the presence of pedestrians both in front of and behind the car and intervene directly activating automatic braking.

EDR - In-vehicle event data recorders: Record vehicle data for incident related events.

The system can indirectly affect road safety, since it can affect driving behaviour, acting on the awareness of continuous monitoring of the way the vehicle is driven.

SENSORS AND CAMERAS. - They assist the driver in parking or reversing; in the most advanced devices, the on-board computer also takes care of carrying out the manoeuvres, turning the steering wheel and acting on the brake and accelerator. It is a device consisting of sensors positioned on the front and rear bumpers that emit ultrasonic waves when they intercept the nearest obstacle, sending information to an electronic board. The parking sensors are hidden in the vehicle's bumpers, so as not to affect the design of the car, and at the moment of the manoeuvre they emit an acoustic signal that becomes greater or more insistent as you approach the obstacle.

Parking sensors have evolved over time to become one of the most advanced driver assistance systems.

ATTENTION: The presence of the sensors requires that the bumpers are always in perfect maintenance conditions to keep them in the correct position: the malfunction of a single sensor can compromise the reliability of the entire ADAS.

DMS - DDD Attention assist: monitors driving behaviour to avoid cases of drowsiness or fatigue, using sensors measuring the movements of the steering wheel and therefore the driving style or video sensors for interpreting the gaze. The driver is alerted with audible and visual signals if the system perceives a significant change from usual behaviour. Driver drowsiness detection systems use cameras or other sensors to monitor the driver's attention. The driver is alerted with audible and visual signals if the system perceives a significant change from usual behaviour or with steering vibrations. System operation varies, whilst some track the frequency of the blink of the eyes and the direction of the gaze, others detect the movements of the driver's head when they indicate a state of sleepiness.

TPMS - TIRE PRESSURE MONITORING.

A tire pressure sensor allows the tire pressure to be monitored at any time, providing a precise reading.

All new cars registered in Europe from 1 November 2014 must be equipped with the tire pressure monitoring system, the TPMS (Tire Pressure Monitoring System). One of the advantages of this innovative technological tool is the ability to monitor the pressure of each individual tire independently. Knowing in real time what the tire pressure of the car is can undoubtedly prove to be a fundamental element for road safety. In fact, the level of friction and grip with respect to the road surface depends on the pressure of the tires, winter or summer, which in turn ensures the right balance between good car performance and a high level of safety. How Does TPMS Work? There are several models of TPMS, which can be basically classified into two categories: Direct: direct TPMS are characterized by the presence of a sensor on each of the 4 wheels, from which the information sent to the central monitor starts. They do not have sensors but are able to calculate the tire pressure by referring to the wheel rotation speed. Thanks to their different detection mechanism, direct pressure sensors can guarantee a more precise and accurate value. The power supply of the system is entrusted to an integrated battery.

BSD - Blind spot detection systems provide information on so-called vehicle blind spots, areas that cannot be easily seen by the driver. They consist of a monitoring system using short-range radar sensors or cameras installed in the lower part of the vehicle's rear-view mirrors. Cameras monitor vehicles approaching from behind alongside the moving car. When another vehicle enters the monitored area, a warning light comes on near the centre rear view mirror. The driver is then warned that another vehicle is approaching from behind and can therefore keep a safe distance.

The Lifesaving Package

On March 26, 2019, the EU introduces a new regulation that imposes stricter safety standards for car manufacturers in order to significantly reduce the number of deaths and injuries on the roads. The regulation updates existing

rules on car safety contained in the Pedestrian Safety Regulation (EC) 78/2009, the General Safety Regulation (EC) 661/2009, and the Hydrogen Safety Regulation (EC) 79/2009⁵. The safety elements provided in the lifesaving package are:

- automatic braking (auto);
- integrated breathalyser (all);
- attention and sleepiness threshold recognition (all);
- distraction monitoring and prevention (all);
- data recording in progress in the accident (all);
- passing crash test for the protection of front passengers (cars / vans);
- emergency brake warning (all);
- expanded head protection zones capable of mitigating collision injuries with vulnerable road users, such as pedestrians and cyclists (cars / vans);
- intelligent speed control systems capable;
- lane maintenance (cars / vans);
- occupant protection against side impacts (cars / vans);
- reversing camera and / or proximity sensors (all) Both should be installed to ensure full safety when reversing through the combined use of the 2 systems;
- tire pressure monitoring (vans / trucks / buses);
- detection and warning of front and side presence of other users (truck / bus);
- greater pedestrian visibility (Truck / Bus).

The complete ADAS training module from ACI is available in appendix 5.1.

2.3 Practical modules with a driving simulator

The modules proposed within this section cover the simulation-based practical training.

The first two modules address preparatory elements for the effective use of the simulator. The third, the most important, covers good practices for the trainers

5

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:035:0032:0046:en:PDF#:~:text=This%20Regulation%20establishes%20requirements%20for,of%20such%20components%20and%20systems.>

related to different scenarios and specific situations during training sessions using the simulator.

Module Component		How to install and configure the simulator software?	
Short Description		Before starting using the Home Study Simulator, all the hardware and software components must be installed and configured. This module component explains how to proceed to be ready to start using it.	
Audience	Novice drivers	Professional/experienced drivers	✓ Trainers
Competency/skills	This module component is not directly linked to CAV driver competencies described in D5.1.		

The content of this module component is sequenced as follows:

The first part is focusing on the description of the minimum hardware requirements necessary for the proper functioning of the HSS. Let's notice that the use of computers that do not correspond to the minimum requirements could lead to frame rate per second drops very low and cause the system to become frozen or react in an unexpected way.

The second part gives information on how to download and parameter all the software components including the driver software operating the steering wheels and the client software operating the simulator.

Finally, it explains the process to obtain all the user credentials required to connect and run the simulator.

The detailed content is described in section 3.1 in deliverable D 5.3.

Module Component		Getting started with the simulator		
Short Description		<p>Before starting using the Home Study Simulator, users need to be aware of the features and possibilities of the software.</p> <p>The module component covers 3 aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -the main features of the Home Study Simulator. -the interface elements of the Home Study Simulator using the steering wheel G39 from Logitech -practicing sessions to become familiar with the simulator 		
Audience	✓	Novice drivers	✓	Professional/experienced drivers
Competency/skills		This module component is not directly linked to CAV driver competencies described in D5.1.		

The content of this module component is sequenced as follows:

a) The main features of the Home Study Simulator

The HSS includes support for approximately 30 minutes driving time per session and more complex events (e.g., dual or single lane roundabouts. It comprised main elements, the 3D simulator built in unity 3D using some purchased assets, city design and the underlying logic.

The city design contains different parts: residential sub-urban area, mixed sub-urban area, city area and city centre each containing relevant scenery and road layouts.

Figure 8 HSS city layout highlighting different areas

For the Urban environmental scenarios, the following features and tasks are available:

- Follow path: The vehicle follows a predetermined path given a subset of waypoints in the scene.
- Roundabout: The vehicle will stop at the junction and drive into the designated exit in the roundabout. There might be vehicles incorporating from the side parking.
- Crossroad: The vehicle will perform the necessary rules concerning crossroads and priorities of driving. There might also be traffic lights or incorporating from the side parking.
- Pedestrian crossing: The user vehicle can encounter different situations while facing a pedestrian crossing and the vehicle adapts to it. For instance, the user might encounter only one or more pedestrians or none, there might be no zebra crossing while a pedestrian is crossing, the pedestrian can have different walking animations (normal walking, looking at the phone, etc.) and there might be objects such as buses blocking visibility. All these situations are randomized.
- Overtake: A vehicle suddenly incorporates from the parking side area in a dual lane street, the vehicle should avoid any collision.
- Parking: At the end, the main vehicle will park in a slot in a parking area.

Figure 9 below illustrates the urban environment in the Home Study Simulator.

Figure 9 Illustrations of urban environment

For the Motorway environmental scenarios, the following features and tasks are available:

- 30 minutes track in a straight road with 3 lanes in a motorway.
- Different kind of vehicles, including trucks for the traffic.
- Tunnel
- Lane closure due to a construction site.
- Lane closure due to an accident.
- Debris in the road.
- Vehicle incorporating from an emergency area.
- Vehicle slowing down to drive into an emergency area.
- Initial and final destination from/to a gas station.

Figure 10 below illustrates the motorway environment in the Home Study Simulator.

Figure 10 Illustrations of motorway environment

b) Interface elements of the Home Study Simulator using the Steering wheel G39 from Logitech

At a glance, the figure 11 illustrates the simple configuration required for the Home Study Simulator. It includes seat, desk, steering wheel and screen that can be easily installed.

Figure 11 Simple configuration of the Home Simulator including seat, steering wheels and screen

The users must also be aware of basic knowledge about the way the software and the steering wheel are interacting. This can be summarised by the figure 12 below which explains the main commands directly available from the steering wheel and from the classical use of pedals.

Figure 12 HSS basic controls explanations

c) Practicing sessions to become familiar with the simulator

To be familiarised with the simulator behaviour, the commands as well as the pedals and steering wheel, a free driving session can be proposed to the users by testing and following one of the driving sections of the track during a few minutes. During this test, they should be able to see how the vehicle is reacting when they perform some driving actions (as braking, stopping, maintaining the correct position on the carriageway).

Module Component	Good practices that the trainer must transmit during the simulation sessions		
Short Description	During the simulation sessions, the trainer observes and detect certain situations with the participants in order to react by giving advices. This module lists situations and typical scenario that can occur in the simulator in urban and in motorway environments and gives elements to the trainer regarding the expected driver response behaviour.		
Audience	Novice drivers	Professional/experienced drivers	✓ Trainers
Competency/skills	<p>List of competencies covered from D5.1</p> <p>1 Knowledge of the capability and competence of the CAV</p> <p>4 Knowledge of the limitations and possible failure of the CAV technologies</p> <p>7 Knowledge of the practical implications of being In the Loop, On the Loop and Out of The Loop</p> <p>8 Do mirror and blind spot checks when preparing to take over control</p> <p>9 Do mirror checks during automated driving</p> <p>10 Do mirror and blind spot checks after resuming manual Driving</p> <p>12 Check yourself (ready to drive, fit, non-driving task stopped, hands free, comfy chair position and ready to use steering wheel and pedals)</p> <p>14 Check for hazards during manual and autonomous Mode</p> <p>15 Assess your position (related to the chair and the steering wheel and pedals)</p> <p>16 Assess the road</p>		

	17 Assess the situation and the next step you will do
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Below is a series of practices for the trainer to react when certain situations arise with the participants during the simulation sessions:

From time to time, the instructor may be required to give reminders to the student about the HSS simulator features and can underline that despite the low-fidelity simulator, he will have to drive in the most realistic way possible.

During the braking and cornering tests, the instructor must correct the learner to lead him to drive the vehicle avoiding it from occupying the carriageway incorrectly (early or delayed braking with respect to the stop lines, traveling through curves and turns by invading the opposite lane or too close to the edge).

Before the simulator allows autonomous driving, the instructor will explain that the latter can be deactivated using a button on the steering wheel or by pressing the brake pedal.

During autonomous driving, the behaviour of the student will be observed and will have to be corrected if he⁶ wants to take back the control of the vehicle before any alert to demonstrate the validity of the autopilot.

When the alert sounds, the instructor must observe whether the tester uses the brake or the appropriate button on the steering wheel to disengage the autopilot.

Should the student take his eyes off the road too frequently and / or keep his hands busy due to an excess of confidence in the autopilot, the instructor must emphasize the following points:

- the on-board systems, not being infallible, may not warn us in time in given conditions,
- or report "false positives", which if not interpreted as such, could induce the driver to carry out incorrect and unnecessarily dangerous manoeuvres.

⁶ Masculine is only used for the sake of conciseness.

The following tables address several scenarios, as highlighted in deliverable D5.1, proposing various situations occurring in a typical urban environment as well as in a Motorway environment, where the take back control process is important. For each of them, the tables give elements to the instructor regarding the expected driver response behaviour.

Table 1 Critical situations and expected driver response behaviour in Urban (intersections) scenario

URBAN SCENARIO INTERSECTIONS	
SITUATION	EXPECTED DRIVER RESPONSE BEHAVIOUR
A) Driver must give way with stopping the vehicle	1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Evaluation of the distance that separates me from the intersection 3) Observation of the context (vertical and horizontal signs and order of precedence) 4) Slow down, stop and give way, whilst continuing to pay attention
B) Driver must give way without stopping the vehicle	1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Evaluation of the distance that separates me from the intersection 3) Observation of the context (vertical and horizontal signs and order of precedence) 4) Slow down, give way and continue paying attention
C) Driver has the right of way	1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Evaluation of the distance that separates me from the intersection 3) Slow down and continue paying attention

Table 2 Critical situations and expected driver response behaviour in Urban (roundabout) scenario

URBAN SCENARIO Roundabout	
SITUATION	EXPECTED DRIVER RESPONSE BEHAVIOUR
A) Driver must give way without stopping the vehicle	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Evaluation of the distance that separates me from the roundabout 3) Observation of the context (vertical and horizontal signs and order of precedence) 4) Slow down and give way 5) Choose the lane to use according to the exit to be taken
B) Driver must give way with stopping the vehicle	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Evaluation of the distance that separates me from the roundabout 3) Observation of the context (vertical and horizontal signs and order of precedence) 4) Slow down and stop, give way before proceeding 5) Choose the lane to use according to the exit to be taken

Table 3 Critical situations and expected driver response behaviour in Urban (crossings) scenario

URBAN SCENARIO CROSSINGS	
SITUATION	EXPECTED DRIVER RESPONSE BEHAVIOUR
A) CROSSWALK/PEDESTRIAN CROSSING	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Evaluation of the distance that separates me from the pedestrian crossing 3) Observation of the context 4) Look ahead and evaluate the danger 5) Start braking before the pedestrian crossing 6) Allow any pedestrian to pass
B) PEDESTRIAN AND CYCLE PATH CROSSING	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Evaluation of the distance that separates me from the crossing 3) Observation of the context 4) Look ahead and evaluate the danger 5) Start braking before the pedestrian and cycle crossings

Table 4 Critical situations and expected driver response behaviour in Motorway scenario

MOTORWAY SCENARIO	
SITUATION	EXPECTED DRIVER RESPONSE BEHAVIOUR
A) CAR THAT OCCUPIES THE PARKING PLOT	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Observe the context (check if the lane on the left is clear) 3) Look ahead and evaluate the danger (check the behaviour of the parked vehicle) 4) Check the rear-view mirrors 5) If necessary, move to the left lane
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot

B) INTENSE TRAFFIC OF TRUCKS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2) Evaluation of the spaces needed to overtake (forward, side and back) 3) Observation of the context (vertical and horizontal signs) 4) Overtake
C) ACCIDENT	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Observe the context and evaluate the danger in front 3) Check the rear-view mirrors to verify the possibility of other direction 4) If necessary, move to the free lane 5) Slow down and follow any indications from traffic officers
D) REDUCTION OF LANES DUE TO ROADWORKS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Observe the context and evaluate the danger 3) Slow down 4) Check the rear-view mirrors 5) Keep the safety distance during any diversion
E) PATH OF A TUNNEL	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Slight braking in order to disengage the autopilot 2) Observe the context and evaluate the danger 3) Keep a safe distance whilst travelling through the tunnel 4) Before leaving I prepare for any gusts of wind and glare

As shown in the table of good practices, a correct assessment of the context is always essential. This is a complex cognitive task, which requires a strong awareness (see appendix 5.2 as an example of awareness training content).

It confirms again the need to have a low cognitive workload, low cognitive fatigue, high situation awareness, few distractions, neutral valence and balanced arousal as displayed in the CAV cognitive and affective model, displayed in figure 4. As mentioned by driving instructors during workshops: drivers need “to know "what to observe" and a great speed of analysis of the situation, as well as a strong predictive ability to project the position of all road users into the imminent future”.

3 Conclusion

This deliverable reports the training approach used in PAsCAL and lists the modules designed for the training experimented in WP5. It presents the theoretical modules taking into account the context of countries of both PAsCAL's driving-school partners (Italia and UK) as well as the practical modules using the Home Study Simulator.

Theoretical modules allow a better understanding of the context of Automation systems.

- How to understand CAV related concepts (6 levels of Autonomous driving, legal perspectives, CAV capabilities and limitations).
- How to manage psychological and physical fitness to drive.

Practical modules allow the use of the Home Study Simulator offering a series of educational scenarios taking up critical situations, identified in deliverable D5.1, that can occur in both urban and motorway environments.

These training modules were tested in UK and Italia by the driving school partners whose sessions outcomes are reported in deliverable D5.3.

Considering work completed within WP5 and with reference to the 'UK Driver Competence Framework' & Pascal [D5.1] – Requirements and competence models for CAV relevant training situations documents, RED are already in the process of adopting the new training module explained earlier urgently within the existing driver training syllabus.

In addition, findings from WP5 are also being used within the development of a new 'Driver Behavioural Training Tool' targeted at acceptance and correct use of existing ADAS systems with a view to encouraging a natural driver progression to higher level of CAV technology as L3 and L4 equipped vehicles come onto the market. The new tool will seek to cover all theory aspects of the new learning to drive syllabus module elements.

A key element to this new module and the development of in-car practical lesson plans will be the adoption into the materials of the 'CHAT' CCheck, Assess and Takeover routine for automated hand back to driver.

This new module could serve both as a part of the current full UK 22 module learning to drive syllabus and also be flexible enough to be used as a standalone training module for experienced and professional drivers during not only a transitional phase of adopting higher levels of CAV but also ongoing.

A review of the existing in-car practical training elements within all the 22 learning to drive syllabus modules is also underway to ensure links to CAV technology, where relevant, have been addressed and added within the materials.

As the CAV technology is constantly evolving, this will take the form of an ongoing review and update process.

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5 Appendix

5.1 ACI's ADAS training module

The ACI Methodology is an integrative teaching method provided to the instructors of all driving schools of the Ready2Go Network.

Specifically, issues linked to road safety are investigated. Among these is the ADAS module, consisting of 120 slides. See below an excerpt of these slides.

Cosa sono Gli ADAS?

Gli ADAS sono dei Sistemi Avanzati di Assistenza alla Guida

Un primo passo verso la sicurezza e la guida autonoma.

A COSA SERVONO?
Evitano gli incidenti o almeno ne riducono le conseguenze.

Secondo il documento "Advanced Driver Assistance Systems" del 2018 della Commissione europea (European Commission)

I sistemi di assistenza alla guida (Advanced Driver Assistance Systems - ADAS) sono definiti come sistemi intelligenti di sicurezza per i veicoli, orientati a migliorare la sicurezza stradale in termini di prevenzione degli incidenti, mitigazione della gravità e protezione nelle fasi post-incidente.

MODULO 6 Advanced Driver Assistance System

READY2GO
L'Associazione che porta in Italia la guida autonoma

Figure 13 Introduction slide about the goal of Adas

Cosa sono Gli ADAS?

Come funzionano gli ADAS?

Attraverso l'uso di sensori, telecamere o addirittura radar. Tali sistemi sono previsti dal **PACCHETTO SALVAVITA** (documento della Commissione Europea).

Tali sistemi sono previsti dal **PACCHETTO SALVAVITA** (documento della Commissione Europea).

A partire dal 2022 tali dispositivi diventeranno obbligatori per i veicoli di nuova omologazione.

Le auto già sul mercato dovranno adeguarsi entro maggio 2024.

MODULO 6 Advanced Driver Assistance System

Figure 14 Training content highlighting key deadlines of Adas regulations

Classificazione ADAS

Esempi di nomenclature
in commercio per diversi ADAS

ADAS Feature	Selection of Marketed Names
Adaptive Cruise Control	Adaptive Cruise Control , Smart Cruise Control, Intelligent Cruise Control, Adaptive Cruise Control with Queue Assist, Dynamic radar cruise control, Distronic Plus, Traffic-Aware Cruise Control
Lane Keeping Assistance	Active Steering Assist, Audi Active Lane Assist, Intelligent Lane Intervention, Lane Departure Alert with Steering Assist, Lane Keep Assist, LaneSense Lane Departure Warning Plus
Blind Spot Warning	Active Blind Spot Assist, Audi Side Assist, Blind Spot Information System, Blind Spot Intervention, Lane Change Alert with Side Blind Zone Alert, Lane Change Assistant (Side Assist), Smart Blind Spot Detection
Surround View Camera	Surround View System, 360° View Monitor, Intelligent Around View Monitor, Multi-terrain Monitor, Bird's Eye View Camera, Surround Vision, Top View Camera System, Wide Front View & Side Monitor

MODULO 6 Advanced Driver Assistance System

Figure 15 ADAS description training slide

Figure 16 Illustration of the whole slide deck dedicated to Adas

5.2 ACI's awareness training content

ACI has created a special format for the dissemination of the key concepts of road education centred on the vehicle, the main causes of road accidents, road safety, speed, and distraction.

This form was also made available to all Italian schools through the portal of the Ministry of Public Education.

The figures below are excerpts of the training module dealing with safety, distraction, or awareness, through slides or videos.

Figure 17. Training content slide dealing with active and passive safety

Le Principali cause di incidente sono:

- 1) **DISTRAZIONE**
- 2) **VELOCITA'**
- 3) **MANCATA DISTANZA DI SICUREZZA**

Figure 18 Training content dealing with the main causes of accidents

Figure 19 Video print screen showing that awareness is a key competency⁷

⁷ Dothetst (2008). *Test Your Awareness: Whodunnit?* Retrieved March 17, 2022 at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ubNF9QNEQLA>

5.3 RED (UK) Complete learning to drive syllabus with theory and practical matrix

This appendix displays the RED (UK) Complete learning to drive syllabus with theory and practical matrix. This syllabus is drafted in line with the UK regulator document National Standard for Driver and Rider Training (Driver and Vehicle Standards Agency, 2020).

Version 2 January 2022

RED's Drive-Learner - *Equipping all drivers with positive practical behaviour through knowledge*

My-RED Progress App link			Syllabus Content	
Module number	Module Name	Short Description	Competency Skills / sub modules	Jargon buster
1	Learning the basics	Introduction to owning and driving a vehicle safely within the law Essential safety cockpit drill for all vehicles	Driving legally Driving safely Checking the vehicle Cockpit drill	As a driver, you possess the responsibility to drive the vehicle safely and within the law. Completing regular vehicle checks, the cockpit drill (a set of checks to make sure the vehicle 'fits' you comfortably and safely) before each use will ensure a

			<p>Keeping up to date with rule changes</p>	<p>safe journey for you, your passengers and others on the road.</p> <p>Owning a vehicle comes with additional responsibilities such as ensuring the vehicle is safe and roadworthy will keep yourself, additional drivers, passengers and other road users safe.</p> <p>All drivers have a responsibility to maintain up to date road safety knowledge and be aware of changes to the rules of driving law.</p>
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2	Security & safe loading	Introduction to knowledge of staying safe & legal whilst	<p>Keeping car secure</p> <p>Transporting passengers</p>	A vehicle provides us with the convenience of transporting passengers and/or loads from one
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		transporting passengers and goods in any vehicle	Transporting loads	location to another. As a driver, it is your responsibility to do this safely and within the law, ensuring that you don't overload the vehicle with passengers/goods and that all passengers and loads are secured correctly and safely.
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3	Controlling the vehicle New CAV inspired module 3a - levels	Standard features: An introduction to the standard features you can expect on most vehicles and best practice use	Accelerator Clutch Gears Foot brake Parking / hand brake Steering / indicators Automatic gear box	In order to drive safely on all types of roads, you need to master the primary controls of the vehicle. Whilst some controls are used on an individual basis, others are used in groups and you will therefore need to develop your multi-tasking skills. All drivers who change the vehicle they use should spend time when first entering the new vehicle to ensure
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	of autonomy and ADAS functions		What to consider when changing vehicles	they fully understand how to use that vehicles controls safely.
3a		<p>An introduction to the levels of autonomy as per the SAE guide.</p> <p>Levels 0 - 5 explained with emphasis on levels 2, 3, & 4, in particular driver assistance features: An introduction to Advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) features you could see on a vehicle and best practice guidance notes</p>	<p>Safe use of the available technology within the vehicle which may include but not limited to the following:</p> <p>Cruise Control</p> <p>Adaptive Cruise Control</p> <p>Parking assist technology</p> <p>Lane departure warning system (LDWS)</p> <p>Automatic emergency braking (AEB)</p>	<p>CAV - Connected Autonomous Vehicle</p> <p>CAV level - According to the SAE (Society of Automotive Engineers) there are 6 levels of driving automation from level 0 having little to no autonomous features, to level 5 which is fully autonomous vehicle</p> <p>Important to consider within this module are features commonly found within level 2, and pending introduction in level 3, which are more usually referred to as ADAS technology.</p>

	<p>Note: Not all features available on current vehicles</p>	<p>Automated Lane Keep System (ALKS)*</p> <p>What to consider when changing vehicles</p> <p>* - Shortly to be introduced</p>	<p>Advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) are groups of electronic technologies that assist drivers in driving and parking functions. Through a safe human-machine interface, ADAS increase car and road safety. ADAS use automated technology, such as sensors and cameras, to detect nearby obstacles or driver errors, and respond accordingly.</p>
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4	Ancillary controls	<p>Introduction to the ancillary controls you can expect on most vehicles and best practice use</p>	<p>Lights (side/dipped/full/hazard /brake/reversing)</p> <p>Washer /wipers (Front & Rear)</p> <p>Demisters / Heaters</p>	<p>These controls are found in the majority of vehicles and help to maintain safety and comfort when driving on all road, weather and lighting conditions.</p>
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			Window controls / Air con Other - including horn	
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5	Use of mirrors	Introduction on use of the vehicle's mirrors to drive safely on the road and around hazards	Signalling Change of direction Change of speed	Using mirrors are paramount to a safe drive. Knowing what's happening behind and around your vehicle and the impact your actions will have on those near you, will ensure you maintain a safe driving environment, not just for you and your passengers, but also for other road users.
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6	Use of signals	<p>Introduction on how to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use signals to inform other road users of your intentions - Use hand signals to support the vehicle's signals - Interpret signals from other road users 	<p>Necessary</p> <p>Correctly</p> <p>Timed</p> <p>Hand signals</p> <p>Interpreting other road users signals</p>	<p>Signals are given to advise other road users, including pedestrians of our intentions. Using the correct signals in plenty of time, will not only inform other road users of what we wish to do, but will allow them sufficient time to act upon them. Understanding other road users signals will help you stay safe on the road, and will shortly include how to interpret the signals or actions of autonomous vehicles.</p>
7	Move off & stop	<p>Introduction on starting to drive and how to master the basic techniques of starting, moving off and stopping in varying situations</p>	<p>Move off & stop</p> <p>Uphill starts / stops</p> <p>Downhill starts / stops</p> <p>Angled move-aways / stops</p>	<p>Before you can drive on busy roads, you need to master the basic techniques of starting, moving off and stopping. You will need to adapt these skills when moving off and stopping close to other parked vehicles and when negotiating, moving off or stopping on hills.</p>

8	Dealing with junctions	Introduction on how to safely negotiate the various road junctions, recognising priorities and your role in keeping traffic moving	<p>Approach junctions</p> <p>Emerge from junctions</p> <p>Crossroads</p> <p>Roundabouts</p> <p>One-way systems</p> <p>Complex / advanced road junctions</p>	<p>Junctions are where two or more roads meet. Negotiating junctions safely can greatly reduce the risk of incidents occurring. Gathering information about the oncoming junction, recognising priorities, supporting and working with other road users are skills you will develop to maintain your progress and help keep traffic moving.</p> <p>Update to incorporate CAV technologies as they advance and the introduction to the Highway Code of 'Hierarchy of road users'</p>
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9	Pedestrian/ other crossings	Introduction on driving safely across the various types of crossings, the routines used on approach and the priorities surrounding these crossings	<p>Pedestrian crossings controlled / uncontrolled</p> <p>Railway crossings</p> <p>Emergency vehicle crossings</p> <p>New style crossings - Tiger etc</p>	<p>Crossings such as pedestrian crossings, railway crossings, emergency vehicle crossings, are locations where roads cross different traffic types and those traffic types have certain rights over those driving or riding vehicles on the road. Knowing the rules for each of the different types of crossings, the routines used and the priorities surrounding them, will ensure a safe drive when negotiating these crossings.</p>
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10	Emergency situations	<p>Introduction on how to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manage emergencies on the road, including breakdowns and the emergency stop - Support emergency response drivers as they make their way through traffic 	<p>Emergency stop</p> <p>Dealing with an emergency</p> <p>Dealing with breakdowns</p> <p>Blue light awareness</p>	<p>Emergencies on the road can occur at any time, such as incidents or accidents, emergency drivers responding to calls or a vehicle breakdown. Knowing how to manage those emergencies and support those dealing with them, can make journeys safer and keep traffic moving wherever possible.</p>
11	Driver Judgement	<p>Introduction on how to proactively use your judgement skills to drive safely, support and work with other road users as well as negotiate various risks and hazards</p>	<p>Meeting traffic</p> <p>Crossing traffic</p> <p>Overtaking</p> <p>Following distance</p> <p>Clearance/obstructions</p> <p>Awareness & planning</p>	<p>To be a good, proactive driver you must be aware of hazards and other road users at all times. This will allow you to predict how your actions will affect them and how their actions will affect you and react in good time. You need to anticipate road, traffic, weather and lighting conditions and act in good time. You will need to take</p>

			<p>Anticipation</p> <p>Other road users including autonomous vehicles</p>	<p>particular care to consider the actions of the more vulnerable groups of road users such as pedestrians, e-scooter riders, cyclists, motorcyclists and horse riders. In the near future you will also have to interact with autonomous vehicles on the road, understanding how to engage with these types of vehicles will be a new challenge to be aware of.</p>
12	Signs & Signals	Introduction on the different types of traffic signs, road markings and signals that warn you of the hazards you may meet on the road ahead	<p>Traffic signs</p> <p>Road markings</p> <p>Traffic controllers</p> <p>Traffic lights</p> <p>From other road users</p>	<p>Traffic signs, road markings and signals provide clues of the possible risks and hazards you may face on the road ahead. Interpreting and using these clues will assist you to drive proactively and manage them as you make your way to your destination.</p>

				Update required to explore how autonomous vehicles may or may not react due to a lack of clear road markings. This cross relates to ADAS module 3a
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13	Vehicle Progress	Introduction on how to make progress safely and tips on how to avoid hesitancy when driving, so not to inconvenience other road users	Appropriate speed Undue hesitation	<p>Driving well below the speed limit can be dangerous and may frustrate other road users who may feel the need to overtake you when it is unsafe to do so.</p> <p>Similarly, being hesitant at junctions, when approaching hazards or when other road users are clearly giving way can result in dangers to other road users as you unexpectedly stop or slow down.</p>
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				<p>Making maximum progress for the road, traffic, weather and lighting conditions without compromising safety, will not only ensure you reach your destination safely and in a timely manner, but will help other road users to do the same.</p>
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14	Use of speed	Introduction on how to drive at the appropriate speed for the road, weather and lighting conditions	Safe use of speed Understanding speed limits	Driving in excess of the speed limit, road, weather or lighting conditions can be dangerous and place other road users and pedestrians at unnecessary risk. Driving at the appropriate speed where you can stop safely within the distance you can see to be clear will not only maximise road safety for you and your passengers, but will provide vital protection for others using the road.
15	Vehicle Positioning	Introduction on positioning the vehicle correctly for the route you wish to take, including stopping	Normal driving Lane discipline Normal stops	Road positioning is key for maintaining road safety. Using traffic signs and road markings will help to determine the correct road position, assist with lane discipline and correct places to stop and will inform other road users of your intentions.

16	Rural & City driving	<p>Introduction on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The considerations to make when driving on different types of roads, including country roads, town and city roads - Supporting and working with other road users on these roads 	<p>Safe driving on country roads</p> <p>Town & city driving</p> <p>Response to other road users</p>	<p>Driving on different types of roads, such as country roads or town and city roads can challenge your driving skills due to the road conditions, the type of road user or traffic experienced.</p> <p>When driving on country roads you may find that bends are often sharper than you think and may come across road users that you wouldn't usually see in residential areas, such as farm vehicles, animals, horse riders just to name a few.</p> <p>When driving on town and city roads you may find that traffic is heavier and hazards may suddenly appear or road conditions may change quickly. Pay</p>
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				<p>attention for pedestrians, who may cross quickly.</p> <p>Driving on these types of roads may test your driving skills and therefore maintaining concentration, being aware of the possible risks and hazards you may face and plan on how to manage them will help to provide a safe drive to your destination.</p>
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17	Dual Carriageway / Motorway	<p>Introduction on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different types of high-speed roads - Driving safely on high-speed roads 	<p>Types of dual carriageways</p> <p>Motorway driving including safe use of Smart Motorways</p> <p>Joining / leaving routines</p>	<p>Dual carriageways and motorways differ from ordinary roads as they are designed to carry traffic at faster speeds and in greater safety. As traffic generally travels faster, conditions may change more rapidly and therefore you need to be alert and</p>
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		<p>- How to support and work with other road users on high-speed roads</p>	<p>Safe following distance Other road users</p>	<p>maintain your concentration throughout.</p> <p>Knowledge of the different types of dual carriageways, motorways, including Smart Motorways will improve your driving experience and safer use of these roads.</p> <p>Joining and leaving routines are skills you will develop, including how to support other road users as they join and leave the dual carriageway/motorway you are travelling along.</p>
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18	Independent driving	<p>Introduction on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to follow road direction signs to your location - Where to position your mobile satellite navigation system to avoid obstructing your view of the road - How to safely use and follow your satellite navigation system's directions to your location 	<p>Driving following road signs</p> <p>Safe use of sat nav</p>	<p>Driving in unfamiliar locations can present its own challenges. Not only do you need to drive safely and take up the correct road position early to make progress, therefore avoiding any actions that could hinder the progress of other road users, you may also need to do this while following instructions to your location. These instructions could be from your passenger, a roadmap, written instructions, road direction signs or a satellite navigation system. Whichever method or system you use, you need to stay aware of your surroundings and maintain your focus on the road ahead.</p>
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19	Safe driving for life in all road/weather conditions	Introduction to driving safely in adverse weather and lighting conditions	<p>Driving in the dark</p> <p>Driving on wet roads</p> <p>Driving in snow/fog</p> <p>Driving in bright sunshine</p> <p>Driving in high winds</p>	<p>Driving in adverse weather and/or lighting conditions can lead to a variety of different hazards, not only from season to season but also from region to region. Adapting your driving skills to match the weather or lighting conditions is just one part of a safe drive. Ensuring your vehicle and equipment is in good condition, regularly checked and serviced is especially important in bad weather or lighting conditions.</p>
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20	Eco-safe driving	Introduction to the principles of eco-safe driving and how to become a more environmentally friendly driver	<p>Fuel-efficient driving</p> <p>Using cruise control for efficiency</p> <p>Choice of fuel for a future vehicle</p>	<p>In 2021 there were just over 40m vehicles using the UK roads. This has an impact on the environment through exhaust fumes and emissions. Driving in an eco-friendly manner will not only reduce your fuel bill and lessen the stress on your vehicle but will also help you to become a more environmentally friendly driver.</p>
21	Reversing Manoeuvres	Introduction to the principles of safely manoeuvring the vehicle, including reversing manoeuvres and parking	<p>Safe use of reverse gear in a straight line</p> <p>Forward bay park</p> <p>Reverse on road right</p> <p>Reverse parallel park</p> <p>Reverse bay park</p>	<p>On route to your destination you may need to complete a reversing manoeuvre to provide access for other road users or on arrival you may need to park your vehicle. Reversing your vehicle can present its own challenges. Not only is it more difficult to see where you are going, but the vehicle will respond differently. When</p>

			<p>Turn in the road</p> <p>Left/Right reverse</p>	<p>manoeuvring your vehicle in reverse, you will need to maintain control of your vehicle and complete effective observations at all times.</p>
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22	<p>Show me/tell me vehicle safety checks</p>	<p>Introduction to the safety checks and tasks required to maintain a vehicle in a safe and roadworthy condition</p>	<p>Show me questions</p> <p>Tell me questions</p> <p>Weekly vehicle safety checks</p> <p>Vehicle handbook & servicing</p>	<p>As a driver, you are responsible for ensuring that any vehicle you drive is safe and roadworthy. Performing regular checks will not only highlight any issues with the vehicle, but help to maintain the integrity of the vehicle and prevent breakdowns.</p>
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